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Targeted drug administration as an accelerator strategy for malaria elimination: a systematic review

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Targeted drug administration as an accelerator strategy for malaria elimination: a systematic review

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Summary of findings table

Should targeted drug administration vs. no targeted drug administration be used for reducing malaria transmission?						
Targeted drug administration compared to no targeted drug administration for reducing malaria transmission						
Outcome	Anticipated absolute effects*		Relative effect (95% CI)	No of participants (studies)	Certainty	Notes
	Risk with no TDA	Risk with TDA (95% CI)				
Prevalence of malaria infection (community level), 1-4 months post-intervention	219 per 1000	186 per 1000 (160 to 219)	RR 0.85 (0.73 to 1.00)	8922 (1 RCT) ¹	⊕⊕⊕⊕ High	TDA results in little to no difference in prevalence of malaria infection at the community level
Serious Adverse Events, randomized trials	0 per 1000	0 per 1000 (0 to 0)	Not estimable	10079 (1 RCT) ¹	⊕○○○ Very low ^{a,b}	The evidence is very uncertain about the effect of TDA on Serious Adverse Events
Serious Adverse Events, randomized trials	2 per 1000	7 per 1000 (2 to 21)	RR 4.19 (1.43 to 12.31)	4916 (1 RCT) ^{2,c}	⊕⊕○○ Low ^d	TDA may result in little to no difference in Serious Adverse Events
Serious Adverse Events, non-randomized trials	0 per 1000	0 per 1000 (0 to 0)	Not estimable	31 (1 observational study) ³	⊕○○○ Very low ^{e,f}	The evidence is very uncertain about the effect of TDA on Serious Adverse Events
Adverse Events, randomized trials	19 per 1000	28 per 1000 (2 to 344)	RR 1.48 (0.12 to 18.02)	4916 (1 RCT) ^{2,c}	⊕⊕○○ Low ^d	TDA may result in a slight increase in AEs
Adverse Events, non-randomized trials	0 per 1000	0 per 1000 (0 to 0)	Not estimable	1094 (1 observational study) ⁴	⊕○○○ Very low ^e	The evidence is very uncertain about the effect of TDA on Adverse Events
Prevalence among those targeted by the intervention*, 0-2 months post-intervention	406 per 1000	61 per 1000 (24 to 154)	RR 0.15 (0.06 to 0.38)	5970 (2 RCT) ^{2,5}	⊕⊕⊕○ Moderate ^g	TDA likely/probably results in a large reduction in prevalence among those targeted by the intervention

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Prevalence among those targeted by the intervention*, non-randomized trials, 1 month post-intervention	315 per 1000	110 per 1000 (69 to 180)	RR 0.35 (0.22 to 0.57)	348 (1 observational study) ^{6,h}	⊕⊕○○ Low ^{g,i}	TDA may result in a reduction in prevalence among those targeted by the intervention
Prevalence among those targeted by the intervention*, non-randomized trials, 1-6 months post-intervention	Both studies reported no malaria cases during the follow-up periods			(2 observational studies) ^{3,4}	⊕○○○ Very low ^{e,f,g}	The evidence is very uncertain about the effect of TDA on prevalence among those targeted by the intervention

*Used as an intermediate outcome for prevalence at the community level; CI: Confidence Interval; RR: Risk Ratio; TDA: Targeted Drug Administration

References

¹Staedke 2018, ²Clarke 2008, ³Marasinghe 2020, ⁴Tseroni 2015, ⁵Rehman 2019, ⁶Opoku 2016

Explanations

^aOutcome was collected in intervention arm only

^bUnable to calculate effect measure in absence of control measures

^cNot corrected for unit of analysis error because of extremely wide confidence intervals.

^dWide confidence intervals

^eCritical overall risk of bias due to inherent biases associated with study design

^fFew patients and few events

^gUsed as a surrogate for prevalence of infection at the community level

^hStudy with two intervention arms. Both arms have been pooled and compared with the control

ⁱModerate risk of bias due to bias due to confounding, bias due to deviations from intended interventions, and no information about bias in measurement of outcomes

Introduction

Rationale

Description of the condition

Malaria is a life-threatening infection caused by the parasite *Plasmodium* and transmitted to humans through the bites of female *Anopheles* mosquitoes. It is estimated that since the year 2000, 1.5 billion cases and 7.6 million deaths have been averted globally, mainly thanks to the vast implementation of malaria preventive, diagnostic and treatment interventions(1). Nevertheless, even though the disease is preventable and treatable, in 2019 there were an estimated 229 million cases in 87 countries and 409 000 deaths(1). Progress has stalled in recent years, urging the malaria community to innovate and maximize the impact of the existing interventions.

Malaria elimination

The Global Technical Strategy for malaria 2016-2030 (GTS), which was endorsed by the World Health Assembly (WHA) in May 2015, set ambitious goals: reductions in global morbidity and mortality from malaria of 90% by 2030 compared to the 2015 baseline, elimination of malaria in 35 countries where it was transmitted in 2015, and prevention of re-establishment wherever the disease had been eliminated(2).

In regards to the elimination milestone, it seems that the world is on track and the number of countries approaching malaria elimination has been increasing since 2000. According to the World Malaria Report 2020(1), 46 countries reported fewer than 10 000 confirmed cases in 2019. In that same year, 27 countries reported fewer than 100 indigenous cases(1).

Accelerating transmission reduction

Thanks to the deployment of effective case management, vector control, chemoprevention, and active use of surveillance, more and more countries are able to successfully reduce malaria transmission and progress towards elimination. In 2017, the World Health Organization (WHO) published The Framework for malaria elimination(3) in an effort to provide guidance on the tools, activities, and dynamic strategies required to achieve interruption of transmission and prevent re-establishment of malaria. While the document emphasizes that all countries should aim for elimination regardless of their transmission intensity, it also highlights that no single intervention or package of interventions will achieve malaria elimination in all countries, rather a set of interventions targeted to the transmission intensity and dynamics of each country. Therefore, accurate stratification (classification of geographical units according to their current transmission intensity) is essential for targeting the interventions effectively.

Once the malaria burden has been largely reduced, specific strategies are needed to achieve elimination. These strategies should accelerate the transmission reduction to a point where intensive surveillance is feasible, should be able to respond to individual cases, and may target specific high-risk groups that are likely to be missed through routine prevention and treatment campaigns(3,4). Some of these “accelerator

strategies” can be applied across a large geographic area such as mass drug administration or mass test and treat, whereas other strategies can target specific populations that are at a higher malaria risk such as targeted drug administration or targeted test and treat(4). The underlying principle of these strategies is that they capture a significant proportion of the reservoir of human malaria parasites in a specific area and therefore reduce malaria transmission, benefitting not only those who receive the intervention but also the community.

A different angle on capturing the reservoir of infection could target groups at high-risk of infection rather than geographic areas. If the majority of infections are accrued within a subset of the population that can be identified by demographic, occupational or exposure characteristics, intervening in the subpopulation could be a more acceptable and cost-effective approach to reducing the reservoir of infection and accelerating towards elimination.

Description of the intervention assessed

Demographic (i.e., age, sex, social characteristics), occupational (i.e., miners, forest goers, peace-keeping forces, agriculture workers, military personnel, and other laborer) and exposure characteristics (i.e., outdoor leisure activities, migration status) may put specific populations at a higher risk of infection, and in areas approaching elimination, these high-risk populations may harbor a large proportion of the human malaria parasite reservoir. To reduce transmission in the general population, targeted drug administration (also known as targeted treatment), defined as the “administration of a full therapeutic course of an antimalarial medicine to a sub-population at high-risk of infection irrespective of infectious status”(4), may be an effective strategy to reduce malaria transmission both among the high-risk population and at the population level.

Why it is important to do this review

In 2015, WHO convened an Evidence Review Group (ERG) to examine the evidence on the use of mass drug administration, mass screening and treatment, and focal screening and treatment for malaria(5). Evidence on the use of mass drug administration was reviewed again in 2018(6), but the recommendations were not endorsed by the Malaria Policy Advisory Group (MPAG, formerly MPAC) and it was decided that future recommendations should follow the process and methodology of the WHO Guidelines Review Committee and the Global Malaria Program Guideline Development Group(7).

Currently, the only population-wide medicine-based accelerator strategy recommended by WHO is mass drug administration for areas approaching elimination or in the countries of the Greater Mekong Subregion where there is concern about increasing parasite resistance to antimalarial medications (3). Nevertheless, many countries have high-risk populations that could be specifically targeted with drug-based strategies such as targeted drug administration or targeted test and treat. This systematic review collected and examined all the available evidence to assess the benefits and harms of targeted drug administration compared to no targeted drug administration.

Objectives

Overall objective

The primary objective of this work was to carry out a comprehensive and systematic review of all available evidence on targeted drug administration for malaria to assess the relative effects (benefits and harms) of targeted drug administration for human malaria transmission reduction when administered to people at higher risk of malaria infection, compared to no targeted drug administration.

Specific objectives

Specific objectives of the review were:

- To determine the benefits and harms when adults and children at higher risk of malaria infection in areas with ongoing transmission or malariogenic potential are administered a therapeutic course of antimalarial medicine, including medication for liver-stage parasites in *Plasmodium vivax* endemic areas, as compared to no intervention,
- To determine which factors may have an epidemiological impact on the effectiveness of the intervention (potential effect modifiers), and
- To identify relevant evidence on contextual factors including values and preferences, acceptability, health equity, resource use, and feasibility.

The benefits and harms assessed are specifically outlined in the outcomes section in **Table 1** below and defined in terms of malaria transmission at the community and population levels, drug resistance and adverse events.

The ultimate goal of this systematic review was to provide evidence to support the development of recommendations related to the activities around targeted drug administration that countries should undertake to help achieve elimination, beyond case management and vector control.

Table 1 displays the details of the population, intervention, comparison and outcomes of the review question.

Table 1. PICO descriptors for Targeted Drug Administration	
Review question: <i>What are the relative effects (benefits and harms) of targeted drug administration compared to no targeted drug administration in adults and children at increased risk of malaria infection?</i>	
Setting	An area with ongoing human malaria transmission or malariogenic potential
Population (targeted group)	Adults and children at increased risk of malaria infection. Risk factors include demographic, occupational and exposure characteristics (including recent travel to a higher transmission area)

Intervention	Administration of a full therapeutic course of an antimalarial medicine
Comparison	No intervention
Outcome (in priority order)	<p>Community (Population) level:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Incidence of malaria infection 2. Prevalence of malaria infection 3. Elimination (defined as 0 indigenous or local cases for a period during the transmission season) 4. Incidence of clinical malaria or number of indigenous malaria cases 5. Drug resistance <p>Among the group targeted by the intervention:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Adverse events 2. Prevalence¹
Timeframe	1-24 months after the start of the intervention
Potential effect modifiers	<p>Level of transmission²</p> <p>Vector control coverage</p> <p>Malaria parasite species (<i>Plasmodium falciparum</i> (Pf), <i>Plasmodium vivax</i> (Pv), <i>Plasmodium ovale</i> (Po) or <i>Plasmodium malariae</i> (Pm)) in the area</p> <p>Antimalarial medication used, including gametocytocide and hypnozoiticide</p>

Methods

Eligibility criteria

Setting characteristics

The study characteristics for eligibility were specific to the PICO descriptors listed in Table 1. Studies selected included research that had taken place in areas with ongoing human malaria transmission or malariogenic potential, which includes no, low, moderate and high transmission settings that may vary between and within countries.

Types of studies

The following types of study designs were included to assess the balance of benefits and harms:

¹ Used as an intermediate outcome for prevalence of malaria infection at the community level.

² The level of transmission will be categorized as High: incidence of about 450/1000 or Pf prevalence of >=35%; Moderate: incidence of 250-450 per 1000 and Pf/Pv prevalence of 10-35%; Low: incidence of 100-250 per 1000 and Pf/Pv prevalence of 1-10%; Very low: incidence of <100 per 1000 and Pf/Pv prevalence <1%(3).

Randomized study designs:

- Cluster-randomized controlled trials (cRCTs) with at least two clusters per arm
- Cluster-randomized cross-over trials with at least two clusters per arm
- Cluster-randomized stepped wedge designs with at least four clusters
- Cluster-randomized factorial designs with at least two clusters per level

Non-randomized study designs:

- Quasi-experimental cluster-controlled trials with at least two clusters per arm
- Controlled before and after studies with at least two clusters per arm and a contemporaneous control group
- Interrupted time series (ITS), controlled or not, with the intervention occurring at a defined point in time, at least three data points collected over one year before the intervention and three data points collected post-intervention
- Uncontrolled before and after studies and before and after studies with historical controls³

Studies were excluded if:

- The follow-up periods for intervention and control were not the same, the timing of baseline and endline surveys was not the same in the intervention and control arms, or the pre- and post-intervention period for ITS studies were different or covered different seasons.
- Background interventions were not evenly distributed between intervention and control arms.
- There were other interventions implemented at the same time in the intervention arm but not in the control arm.

Types of participants

Adults and children living in areas with ongoing transmission or malariogenic potential were included and analyzed by transmission setting. Specifically, those defined as at high risk for infection, based on demographics (i.e. age, sex, social characteristics), occupational (i.e. miners, forest goers, peace-keeping forces, agriculture workers, military personnel, and other laborers) or other exposure characteristics (i.e. outdoor leisure activities, migration status), including recent travel to a higher transmission area, were targeted. Of note, special attention was paid to studies that were targeting populations thought to be important reservoirs of infection such as school-aged children, migrant labor or refugees originating from a malaria endemic region, or populations known to be the remaining foci of transmission in areas approaching elimination, such as forest workers in forested areas of the Greater Mekong Subregion (GMS).

³ These studies were judged to have a critical risk of bias

Types of interventions

Intervention arm: For the purpose of this review, targeted drug administration was defined as the “administration of a full therapeutic course of an antimalarial medicine to a sub-population at high-risk of infection irrespective of infection status”(4), including treatment for *Plasmodium vivax* and *Plasmodium ovale* liver-stage parasites, to reduce malaria transmission among both the high-risk population and the population level. Treatments may be synchronous or asynchronous, intermittent or one-off. Studies testing the impact of the administration of antimalarial drugs in the form of chemoprevention to clear individual parasite infections (i.e., intermittent preventive treatment in pregnancy or seasonal malaria chemoprevention) were not included. Likewise, studies administering drugs to a specific population based on geographic areas instead of risk factors (i.e., hotspots of higher transmission) were excluded.

Control arm: No intervention.

Background interventions: We anticipated that existing control efforts would include background interventions that provided adequate access to case management, testing and treatment for the populations within an intervention area. For included studies that have described background interventions that were co-administered during the intervention or where the comparison or control arm included the standard of care, details were recorded. This may have included chemoprevention strategies and/or passive case detection among other ongoing surveillance activities taking place in the region.

Exclusion criteria: This review did not assess or evaluate the efficacy of antimalarials, drug regimens/ dosing, or diagnostic tests. Likewise, the supply chain, resource management, access to care, and quality of care were not evaluated. While we are aware that these all play a significant role in overall intervention effectiveness, we did not individually assess these program characteristics.

Time of follow-up

Studies with follow-up periods from 1 to 24 months were included. For the meta-analysis, follow-up periods ranging from 1 to 24 months after the start of the intervention were extracted. Time points outside of this range were excluded, but all time points within this period were included.

Outcomes

Studies had to report at least one of the following to be included: one or more outcomes, data on contextual factors, or mathematical modelling results. For outcomes that specified parasitological confirmation, the possible diagnostic approaches included malaria rapid diagnostic tests (RDT), microscopy, or molecular methods such as polymerase chain reaction (PCR).

The following outcomes were assessed:

- incidence of infection at the community level
- prevalence of infection at the community level
- elimination (defined as 0 indigenous or local cases for a period during the transmission season)
- incidence of clinical malaria
- drug resistance

- adverse events among the group targeted by the intervention⁴
- prevalence among the group targeted by the intervention⁵

Contextual factors

For the assessment of the evidence of contextual factors relevant to implementation and operational aspects of the intervention, all study designs, including qualitative studies were included.

The following contextual factors were assessed:

Values and preferences: the values and preferences of the individuals and populations affected by the recommendation with respect to the outcomes associated with the intervention.

Health equity: extent to which the intervention benefits all populations, does not discriminate against anyone on the basis of sex, age, ethnicity, culture, language, sexual orientation or gender identity, disability status, education, socioeconomic status, residence or any other characteristic. This could include whether the benefits and harms are equally distributed and whether the intervention is equally affordable and accessible to all.

Acceptability: the extent to which those benefiting from an intervention as well as other relevant stakeholder groups consider the intervention to be appropriate, based on anticipated or experienced cognitive and emotional responses to the intervention.

Feasibility: legal barriers to implementation, interaction with the existing health system, need for and use of the existing health workforce or other resources or programmatic considerations.

Resource use: cost, overall economic impact, cost-benefit.

Mathematical modelling studies

Modelling studies were used to provide evidence for operational considerations, such as the timing of the intervention, coverage rates, number of rounds, etc. These studies were further categorized as:

- simulation mathematical studies based on assumptions
- mathematical modelling studies grounded in empirical data from specific study sites

⁴ Meant to be distinguished from the community-level outcomes, but refers not only in the study arm that got the intervention, but both intervention and control arms.

⁵ Although the PICO question referred to “transmission”, which is a community-level outcome, it was decided to include prevalence among the group targeted by the intervention as a proxy indicator of the potential effect at the community level. Finding no effect of the intervention among the targeted group would be a reliable proxy for no effect on community transmission. However, a positive effect among the targeted group would not be a reliable proxy for the effect on community transmission.

Timing of outcome measurements

The pre-intervention of baseline period was defined as 1-12 months prior to the first round of targeted drug administration. The post-intervention period refers to the time period following the last round of targeted drug administration.

Information sources

The studies included in this review were identified by searching in academic publications, relevant electronic databases and the grey literature without timeframe limitation. Pre-defined search terms and relevant subheadings, as well as keywords related to malaria, antimalarials, diagnosis and treatment, were used.

The following sources were included(4):

- Bibliographic databases: MEDLINE (PubMed), LILACS, EMBASE (Ovid), the Cochrane Library.
- Other relevant databases: ZETOC, Armed Forces Pesticide Management Board (AFPMB), The Archives of the World Health Organization, US National Institute of Health Ongoing Trials Register (clinicaltrials.gov), ISRCTN registry, The WHO's International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (WHO ICTRP), and the MESA Track database.
- Conference proceedings: American Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene (ASTMH) Annual Meetings, Johns Hopkins Bloomberg School of Public Health Future of malaria research Symposium, Keystone/MESA Symposium, Women in Malaria Conference, Doctors Without Borders (MSF) Scientific Days 2021, Asia Pacific Malaria Elimination Network (APMEN) Journal Clubs (TechTalks), 6th Southern Africa Malaria Research Conference.
- Researchers and organizations within the field.
- Reference lists: the reference lists of studies identified and included in the review were reviewed for additional relevant studies.

All studies that met eligibility criteria regardless of language or publication status (published, unpublished, in press, and in progress) were included for consideration in this review.

Search strategy

A preliminary search was conducted to scope the state of the art, assess appropriate search keywords and terms and collect background information on malaria elimination strategies. This scoping search strategy was developed in consultation with a librarian from the University of Barcelona.

The final search strategy for the review was developed in collaboration with a systematic review information specialist and was conducted in March 2021. This final search strategy is presented in **Appendix 1**.

Given that the Centers for Disease Prevention and Control (CDC) was undertaking a systematic review on mass drug administration, if any study relevant to the targeted drug administration review was identified in their search, it was added for review of the title and abstract for possible inclusion.

Data management

To manage records and data throughout the review, the software system Zotero⁶ was used for the storage of identified articles. Corresponding shared spreadsheets and documents were stored using G-suite tools. The overall project details for studies included in the reviews are stored in the Malaria Eradication Scientific Alliance (MESA) tracking tool (MESA Track⁷). In addition, ongoing projects have been compiled in MESA Track as a “Deep Dive” to allow for reference to projects that may generate relevant results in the future. The title/abstract and full-text reviews were conducted in Eppi-Reviewer 4.0 and Eppi-Reviewer Web. All data extracted from selected studies were recorded in an excel spreadsheet and the outcome data and analysis analyses were conducted in Eppi-Reviewer 4.0 and Eppi-Reviewer Web⁸.

Selection process

Two authors from the systematic review team independently reviewed abstracts and titles from the retrieved articles. For any discrepancies or disagreements in inclusion or exclusion by the two authors, the remaining systematic review team members assessed the title and abstract for agreement. All studies identified as potentially eligible based on the title and abstract reviews were retrieved, and the full report was assessed for eligibility by both authors, independently. The final selection for both the title/abstract screening and full-text screening was made using an eligibility criteria checklist to record how each study was assessed based on study inclusion/exclusion criteria. For any discrepancies or disagreements in inclusion by the two authors, the remaining systematic review team members assessed the study for inclusion. In the event of still disagreement, the WHO methodologist and Elimination Guidelines Development team lead were consulted for final determination. The final list of studies included in the full-text review was shared with the GDG, WHO methodologist and malaria elimination team lead for agreement. The abstract/title screening process and full-text review processes were tested in a calibration exercise with the study authors using the Eppi-Reviewer 4.0 and/or Web tools. Each author practised the abstract/title screening and full-text review independently, followed by the development of a written standard operating procedure (SOP) to codify the screening process. The authors then conducted an exercise to compare the screening outcomes for the abstract/ title and full-text review on a subset of articles using the corresponding SOPs in the Eppi-Reviewer tool.

⁶ Zotero is a project of the Corporation for Digital Scholarship, a nonprofit organization dedicated to the development of software and services for researchers and cultural heritage institutions, and is developed by a global community. Website: www.zotero.org

⁷ MESA Track is a living database which captures research projects and institutions' portfolios in malaria elimination and eradication. The tool was developed and managed by the MESA Alliance, hosted at the Barcelona Institute for Global Health and funded by a grant from the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation. Website: mesamalaria.org/mesa-track

⁸ Eppi-Reviewer is an application for literature reviews, including systematic reviews, meta-analyses, 'narrative' reviews and meta-ethnographies. The tool was developed and maintained by the EPPI-Centre at the Social Science Research Unit of the UCL Institute of Education, University of London, UK. Website: eppi.ioe.ac.uk. Eppi-Reviewer was last updated on 15 October 2020 (version 4.11.5.1).

After data extraction and categorization of study information, the included studies were assessed for meta-analysis by the primary author with confirmation by a second review team member; potential for pooled analyses were based on outcome data and time points for the intervention and follow-up timeframe. **Figure i and Figure ii in Appendix 2** represent the flow diagram for the review methodology and the adapted PRISMA flow diagram for study synthesis and meta-analysis.

Data collection process

Of the studies selected for inclusion in the review, key data was extracted from study documents by the primary author, with confirmation by the secondary authors by separately extracting data into an abridged data extraction table and comparing it with the data extracted by the primary author. For any information not specified in study documents, the principal investigators for the study were contacted for consultation on missing and additional information and asked to share further information. For data that could not be retrieved, missing data was not added by imputation methods, rather the study was assessed for an alternative qualitative summary analysis for specific outcomes with missing data.

Data items

The data extracted from the studies included both descriptive data and study calculations and measurements (where relevant) to assess comparability and eligibility for data synthesis and pooled analyses. Variables for data extraction included: study design, setting, demographics, methodology, treatment, comparison, time period, baseline characteristics, intervention, outcomes, study biases, background interventions, and any other contextual study information that was informative in assessing confidence as evidence. The review authors developed the data extraction forms to capture the necessary study variables and conducted a practice exercise for the data collection process. **Table i in Appendix 2** provides further details for all the variables for which data were sought.

Study risk of bias assessment

The primary author independently assessed the risk of bias in individual studies included in the review, and a secondary author performed an abridged assessment at the domain level for comparison and agreement.

Different tools to assess the risk of bias were used depending on the design of each study. For RCTs, the Cochrane 'Risk of bias' (RoB) RoB2 tool(8) was used with an assessment reported as low risk, some concerns, high-risk, or unclear and with the results displayed as summary graphs. The RoB assessment was conducted at the outcome level for each study. The RoB2 tool for cluster randomized trials that addresses the additional criteria described in section 23.1.2 in the Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions was used specifically for cluster-RCTs(9). For non-randomized controlled trials and ITS trials, the 'Risk of bias' tool (ROBINS-I) from the Cochrane Effective Practice and Organization of Care (EPOC) Group(10) was used with an assessment reported as low risk, moderate risk, serious risk, critical risk, or no information. If any domain reached a critical risk of bias, the assessment was discontinued, as further evaluation would not influence how the certainty of the evidence was assessed. All outcomes from uncontrolled before-and-after studies and before-and-after studies with historical

controls were assigned a critical overall risk of bias due to the inherent biases associated with the study design(4). These studies were only included if there were no other studies available or if there were no other studies for an important subgroup. If these studies were included, a sensitivity analysis was conducted, assuming there were sufficient other studies, by conducting the meta-analysis without the studies with critical risk of bias and then conducting a sensitivity analysis by including them.

For all studies that were considered to be at critical risk of bias, a subsidiary descriptive analysis and report of their estimates of effect were generated. A sensitivity analysis was planned to be conducted for these studies to describe the effect of confounding(4).

The risk of bias assessments were conducted using predefined criteria for Grading of Recommendations, Assessment, Development and Evaluation (GRADE) as described in the confidence in cumulative evidence section below. Any disagreements or discrepancies between reviewers was resolved through discussion or by consulting the other systematic review members. If a consensus was not reached, the systematic review team consulted the WHO methodologist(4).

Effect measures

Synthesis methods

To decide which studies were eligible for each synthesis, we tabulated the study intervention characteristics and compared for each outcome. For data where a quantitative synthesis could be conducted, meta-analysis was performed to combine and summarize the results of the included studies.

For dichotomous outcomes (e.g., infection, adverse events, etc.) of randomized studies, we extracted the crude number of cases, number of participants targeted in the intervention, those reporting adverse events, and the total number of participants assessed for the outcome in each study arm. For each outcome the crude proportions or ratios were recorded, as well as the total person time at risk or population at risk in each study arm for incidence rates. Measures of variance (e.g. standard error, intercorrelation coefficient or coefficient of variance) were included if provided in the study methods. We recorded both crude and adjusted measures of effect (e.g. risk ratio (RR), odds ratio (OR), rate ratio (RR), or mean difference (MD)) with 95% confidence intervals (CI). For non-randomized studies, we extracted adjusted measures of intervention effects that attempted to control for confounding including RRs and/or rate ratios.

Unit of analysis

For cRCTs, measures of effect adjusted for clustering were used if available. The raw data was adjusted using the intracluster correlation coefficient (ICC) values and mean cluster size obtained from the study or authors, and where unavailable, it was extrapolated from similar studies. If unable to obtain an ICC value or appropriate estimate, the adjusted effect estimate reported in the study was inputted into Eppi-Reviewer (or another application for systematic reviews such as Revman) without further analysis. If studies had more than one intervention arms, treatment arms were combined if appropriate.

Data synthesis

Data from randomized and non-randomized studies were pooled separately. We used random-effects meta-analysis to report a pooled effect estimate when appropriate. If there were only two studies available for synthesis, fixed-effect meta-analysis was used if meta-analysis was appropriate.

Assessment of heterogeneity

To test for heterogeneity in the included studies we used a chi-squared (X^2) statistic test for study effect measures, assessing a P-value of <0.05 as significant. We also assessed heterogeneity using the degree of inconsistency (I^2) to calculate the percentage of total variation across studies that was not due to chance. We interpreted the inconsistency across study outcomes effect measures according to a scale of very low, low, moderate, or high with values of $<25\%$, $26-50\%$, $51-74\%$ and $>75\%$, respectively(11). If there was substantial heterogeneity (I^2 statistic value above 50%) and inconsistency in the direction of the effect with non-overlapping CIs, then we did not perform a meta-analysis. Rather, we planned to perform subgroup analysis as described below to see if we could reduce heterogeneity.

Subgroup analysis

For the prioritized potential effect modifiers, it was planned that data would be stratified for subgroup analysis, with at least two studies in each subgroup. The subgroups to be assessed were:

- Level of transmission
- Vector control coverage
- Malaria parasite species (*Pf*, *Pv*, *Po* or *Pm*) in the area
- Antimalarial medication used, including gametocytocide and hypnozoiticide

Where quantitative synthesis was not appropriate, due to limited number of studies and inability to reduce substantial heterogeneity, the subgroup analysis was not performed and the resultant data has been summarized based on key findings in a narrative description. Likewise, for the contextual factors, it was planned that data would be stratified using the categories listed above and textually summarized.

Reporting bias assessment

Most reporting biases are accounted for within the approach used for the identification of studies for the review. Meta-biases such as selective reporting of bias were assessed in part by the RoB assessments being conducted at the study level and in the data extraction process, which allowed for the identification of gaps in reported outcomes across studies. In particular, for within study selective reporting bias for included randomized studies, if a trial registration was available, the registration was checked for consistency in methodology, outcomes planned and what was reported in the study. For publication bias, funnel plots were planned to be generated if there were at least 10 studies included in the analysis.

Certainty assessment

The certainty of the evidence for each intervention across each outcome measure was assessed using the GRADE method (Table 2). Randomized studies were initially ranked as high certainty of evidence and non-randomized studies were initially ranked as low. The certainty of evidence was downgraded if there was evidence of the following 1) risk of bias, 2) imprecision, 3) inconsistency of evidence, 4) indirectness and 5) publication bias. Certainty of evidence for non-randomized studies could be upgraded if all domains were rated as low risk and there was evidence of 1) large magnitude of effect, 2) evidence of a dose-response relationship, or 3) where it was likely that residual confounding would increase the magnitude of effect.

Table 2. GRADE Criteria

Certainty	Interpretation
Very Low	The authors believe that the true effect is likely to be markedly different from the estimated effect
Low	The authors believe that the true effect might be markedly different from the estimated effect
Moderate	The authors believe that the true effect is probably close to the estimated effect
High	The authors have a lot of confidence that the true effect is similar to the estimated effect

To ensure consistency in judgements around precision and size of absolute effect measures of interventions to reduce transmission, thresholds for determining public health value of interventions were determined as listed in Table 3:

Table 3. Categorization of effect sizes

Species and transmission level	Effect size	Absolute difference in prevalence	Absolute difference in annual incidence
<i>Plasmodium falciparum</i> – Very low to low	Little to no	0 to 0.03% (0-0.3 per 1000)	0 to 3 per 1000 person-year
	Slight or some (public health value threshold)	0.04% to 0.1% (0.4 to 1 per 1000)	4 to 10 per 1000 person-year
	Large	>0.1% (>1 per 1000)	> 10 per 1000 person-year
<i>Plasmodium falciparum</i> – Moderate to high	Little to no	0 to 10% (0 to 100 per 1000)	0 to 250 per 1000 person-year
	Slight or some (public health value threshold)	10 to 20% (100 to 200 per 1000)	250 to 333 per 1000 person-year
	Large	>20% (>200 per 1000)	>333 per 1000 person-year
<i>Plasmodium vivax</i>	Little to no	0 to 5% (0 to 50 per 1000)	0 to 125 per 1000 person-year
	Slight or some (public health value threshold)	5% to 10% (50 to 100 per 1000)	125 to 250 per 1000 person-year
	Large	>10% (>100)	>250 per 1000 person-year

For the summary of findings statements, we considered both the size of the effect and the certainty of evidence assessments (**Table 4**)(12).

Table 4. Summary of findings statements criteria				
Effect size	Certainty			
	High	Moderate	Low	Very low
Large	TDA results in a large reduction/increase in outcome	TDA likely/probably results in a large reduction/increase in outcome	TDA may result in a large reduction/increase in outcome	
Slight or some	TDA results in a slight reduction/increase in outcome	TDA likely/ probably results in little to no difference in outcome	TDA may reduce/increase outcome slightly	The evidence is very uncertain about the effect of TDA on outcome
Little to no	TDA results in little to no difference in outcome	TDA likely/ probably results in little to no difference in outcome	TDA may result in little to no difference in outcome	

TDA: targeted drug administration

Review of GRADE summary of findings tables and criteria was conducted by the WHO methodologist and malaria elimination team lead for agreement.

For the contextual factors assessed in the review, we planned to use the ‘Confidence in the Evidence from Reviews of Qualitative research’ (GRADE-CERQual) approach. The GRADE-CERQual approach provides a certainty or confidence of a qualitative synthesis of studies using the following four components: 1) the methodological limitations, 2) coherence, 3) the adequacy of data supporting a review finding, and 4) the relevance of data from primary studies(13). We planned to assess and interpret each contextual factor using the criteria adapted from the descriptive interpretations by Lewin et al(14). However, given the low number of studies included for contextual factors and the fact that no synthesis for contextual factors was possible, it was decided to only produce textual summaries of findings for each study.

Results

Study selection

A total of 3179 records were identified: 2970 via searching databases, 137 from registers, and 72 via other methods (e.g., websites, organizations and citation searching). Before the screening, 838 records were removed due to duplication, with a total of 2341 records to be screened against title and abstract eligibility (2269 identified via databases and registers and 72 identified via other methods). Of these, 69 were assessed for full-text eligibility criteria. After the full-text screening, five studies were included for assessment of outcome data (six reports) and two studies were included for assessment of contextual factors. The detailed Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) Flow Diagram is presented in **Appendix 3**, which also includes the reasons for exclusion.

Three studies appeared to meet the inclusion criteria but were excluded because they were still in progress with no published results (See [Ongoing studies](#)).

Study characteristics

Included and excluded studies are described in detail in the [Characteristics of studies tables](#).

Included studies

Five studies met criteria for inclusion: two cRCTs, conducted in Uganda (**Staedke 2018**(15) and **Rehman 2019**(16)) and Kenya (**Clarke 2008**(17)); one controlled before and after study conducted in Ghana (**Opoku 2016**(18)); and two uncontrolled before and after studies conducted in Sri Lanka (**Marasinghe 2020**(19)) and Greece (**Tseroni 2015**(20)). Additionally, two articles were assessed for contextual factors: one article for resource use (**Temperley 2008**(21)), and one article for acceptability (**Matangila 2017b**(22)).

Descriptive characteristics of the five included studies are summarized in **Table 3** and described in detail in the [Characteristics of included studies tables](#).

Interventions

Staedke 2018(15) and **Rehman 2019**(16) reported on a cRCT that took place in Jinja district, Uganda, in 2014. Monthly intermittent preventive treatment with sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine was administered to children aged five to 20 years in 84 primary schools. **Clarke 2008**(17) reported on a cRCT that took place in Bondo district, Western Kenya, in 2005-2006. Three rounds of intermittent preventive treatment with sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine and amodiaquine were deployed every four months, targeting children aged five to 18 years attending 30 primary schools. **Opoku 2016**(18) described the findings from a three-arm, open-label, before-after intervention study including a control arm that was implemented in Kassena-Nankana Districts in the Upper East Region of Ghana in 2011. Three rounds every three months of intermittent preventive treatment with artemether-lumefantrine were administered to children aged six to 15.

Marasinghe 2020(19) described an uncontrolled before and after study deploying Mass Radical Treatment to a group of foreign workers in Sri Lanka in 2018. On the other hand, **Tseroni 2015**(20) reported the results of an uncontrolled before and after study that conducted targeted drug administration with chloroquine and primaquine to immigrants living in the epicenter of the 2011 malaria outbreak in Evrotas, Southern Greece, in 2013 and 2014.

Outcomes

Prevalence of infection at the community level was reported in **Staedke 2018**(15) at 1-4 months post-intervention. The intervention was delivered from June to December 2014 and cross-sectional community surveys in randomly selected households were done at baseline and in January to April, 2015. Prevalence was measured by microscopy.

Serious Adverse Events (SAEs) were reported in the two cRCTs (**Clarke 2008**(17) and **Staedke 2018**(15)) within 28 days of any treatment and during the delivery of the intervention, respectively. **Staedke 2018**

did not monitor adverse events in the control arm. Of the non-randomized studies, SAEs 1-5 months post-intervention were also monitored in **Marasinghe 2020**(19). For cRCTs, Adverse Events (AEs) were reported in **Clarke 2008**(17), within 28 days of any treatment, and for non-randomized studies, **Tseroni 2015**(20) reported AEs for 1-6 months post-intervention.

Prevalence of infection among the targeted populations was measured by microscopy and reported in the two cRCTs at 1-2 months post-intervention (**Clarke 2008**(17)) and at the last month of intervention (**Rehman 2019**(16)). The controlled before and after study, **Opoku 2016**(18), reported prevalence of infection among the targeted population at 1 month post-intervention, also measured by microscopy. In the two non-randomized studies all individuals treated were screened for parasitemia during the follow-up periods of five months post-intervention (**Marasinghe 2020**(19)) and at least six months post-intervention (**Tseroni 2015**(20)).

Contextual factors

The costs and cost-effectiveness of delivering intermittent preventive treatment through schools were reported in **Temperley 2008**(21), based on the study reported in **Clarke 2008**(17). The perception of parents and teachers about intermittent preventive treatment for malaria in school children was assessed in **Matangila 2017b**(22).

Excluded studies

Fifty-seven articles were excluded after full-text screening due to the following reasons: incorrect intervention (n=12), incorrect population (n=4), incorrect study focus area (n=6), incorrect study design (n=13), cross-referenced article (n=8), incorrect background interventions (n=2), incorrect comparison (n=1), or because a full report could not be retrieved (e.g., abstract, protocol or other document and ongoing studies) (n=11). All full-text studies that did not meet eligibility criteria are listed with their reasons for exclusion in the [Characteristics of excluded studies table](#).

Table 5. Characteristics of included studies					
Study	Location	Year(s)	Study design	Intervention	Outcomes reported
Staedke 2018(15) Rehman 2019(16)	Eastern Uganda	2014	cRCT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Target population: school children • Intervention: IPT • Comparator: standard of care • Drug: DHA/PPQ • Rounds: six, monthly 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prevalence of infection at the community level (1-4 months post-intervention) • SAEs (measured during delivery of intervention, month 0) • Prevalence of infection among those targeted (last month of intervention, month 0)
Clarke 2008(17)	Western Kenya	2005- 2006	cRCT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Target population: school children • Intervention: IPT • Comparator: placebo • Drug: SP/AQ • Rounds: three, every four months 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prevalence of infection among those targeted (1-2 months post-intervention) • SAEs and AEs (within 28 days of any treatment)
Opoku 2016(18)	Upper East Region Ghana	2011	cBAF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Target population: school children • Intervention: IPT • Comparator: treatment with anthelmintic • Drug: AL • Rounds: three, every three months 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prevalence of infection among those targeted (1 month post-intervention)
Marasinghe 2020(19)	South- western Sri Lanka	2018	uBAF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Target population: migrant workers • Intervention: mass radical treatment • Comparator: not applicable • Drug: chloroquine + primaquine (low dose) • Rounds: single round 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prevalence of infection among those targeted (1-5 months post-intervention)
Tseroni 2015(20)	Southern Greece	2013- 2014	uBAF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Target population: migrant workers • Intervention: mass radical treatment • Comparator: not applicable • Drug: chloroquine + primaquine (high dose) • Rounds: 1, every year 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prevalence of infection among those targeted (1-6 months post-intervention)

AEs: adverse events; AL: artemether-lumefantrine; cBAF: controlled before and after; DHA/PPQ: dihydroartemisinin- piperazine; IPT: intermittent preventive treatment; SAEs: serious adverse events; SP/AQ: sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine + amodiaquine; uBAF: uncontrolled before and after.

Risk of bias in studies

Detailed explanations for the judgements are provided in the [Characteristics of included studies tables](#).

cRCTs

Assessments for risk of bias for the outcomes assessed in the two cRCT (**Staedke 2018**(15), **Rehman 2019**(16) and **Clarke 2008**(17)) are summarized in **Figures 1 and 2**.

Figure 1. Risk of Bias summary for the outcomes assessed in the cRCTs. D1a: randomization process; D1b: timing of identification or recruitment of participants; D2: deviations from the intended interventions; D3: missing outcome data; D4: measurement of the outcome; D5: selection of the reported result.

Study	Outcome	D1a	D1b	D2	D3	D4	D5	Overall	
Staedke 2018	Prevalence community	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Staedke 2018	SAEs	+	+	+	-	+	+	-	-
Rehman 2019	Prevalence targeted	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Clarke 2008	AEs (including SAEs)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Clarke 2008	Prevalence targeted	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

Figure 2. Risk of Bias summary for the cRCTs by percentage.

Domain 1a: Randomization process

All studies were rated as low risk of bias in terms of the randomization process. It was considered that both studies used acceptable randomization processes, such as restricted randomization (**Staedke 2018**(15)) or computer-generated randomization (**Clarke 2008**(17)).

D1b: timing of identification or recruitment of participants

Risk of bias for recruitment of participants was rated as low for all outcomes.

D2: deviations from the intended interventions

It was considered that there were no notable deviations from the intended interventions in all outcomes assessed. Even though both studies were unblinded, there was nothing to indicate that the intervention had any deviations from its intended format based on the trial context.

D3: missing outcome data

For the prevalence outcome (at the community and among those targeted by the intervention), both studies reporting these effects were rated as low risk. For adverse events, one study was rated as high-risk (**Staedke 2018(15)**) as the outcome was not measured in the comparison arm.

D4: measurement of the outcome

For the prevalence outcome (at the community level and among those targeted by the intervention), both studies reporting these effects were rated as low risk, as measurement of the outcomes was done by staff unaware of study group assignments. For adverse events, even though **Staedke 2018(15)** was not blinded and drugs differed in taste in **Clarke 2008(17)**, it was still considered that risk of bias was low as adverse events were assessed by experienced personnel and it was unlikely that participants reported presence of adverse events due to awareness of the arm to which they were assigned.

D5: selection of the reported result

Risk of bias for selection of the reported result was rated as low for all outcomes, as reported primary and secondary outcomes were the same as reported in clinicaltrials.gov.

Controlled before and after study

Figures 3 and 4 summarize the risk of bias assessment for the controlled before and after study (**Opoku 2016(18)**).

Figure 3. Risk of Bias summary for the controlled before and after study.

D1: Bias due to confounding

Bias due to confounding was rated as moderate because the study reported crude prevalence proportions based on the number of study participants without accounting for other potential influences to study outcomes.

D2: Bias due to selection of participants into the study

Bias due to selection of participants was rated as low because it was considered that all participants who would have been eligible for the target trial were included in the study and the start of follow up and start of intervention coincided for each participant.

D3: Bias in classification of interventions

It was considered that there was low risk of bias in classification of interventions, because there was nothing to suggest that the intervention status was not well defined and classified.

D4: Bias due to deviations from intended interventions

Given that the planned study design had to be changed from a randomized controlled trial to a before-after design because of limitations due to funding constraints and expansion to accommodate other thematic areas, it was considered there was moderate risk of bias due to deviations from intended interventions.

D5: Bias due to missing data

Bias due to missing data was rated as low because the study had a 97% of follow-up.

D6: Bias in measurement of outcomes

Since there was no description of blinding of outcome assessment, we do not have information to assess bias in the measurement of outcomes.

D7: Bias in selection of reported result

Risk of bias for selection of the reported result was rated as low for the prevalence outcome, as reported primary and secondary outcomes were the same as reported in clinicaltrials.gov.

Uncontrolled before and after studies

The two uncontrolled before and after studies (**Marasinghe 2020**(19) and **Tseroni 2015**(20)) were rated as critical overall risk of bias due to the inherent biases associated with the study design and therefore were not assessed further using a risk of bias tool.

Results by outcome

Effects reported on prevalence of malaria infection at the community level

Staedke 2018(15) reported data on prevalence of infection at the community level at 1-4 months post-intervention through cross-sectional community surveys in randomly selected households and found a

lower community-level prevalence in the intervention clusters than in the control clusters (19% vs 23%, adjusted RR 0.85, 95% CI 0.73-1.00).

Effects reported on SAEs and AEs

Staedke 2018(15) monitored SAEs in all intervention participants during the delivery of the intervention. 17 SAEs were reported, including two deaths (one from a road traffic accident and one from a tetanus infection, both unrelated to the drug). Among the remaining 15 serious adverse events, two were considered as possibly related to the drug administration. Adverse events were not monitored in the control arm. **Clarke 2008**(17) monitored AEs for three days after each treatment and a further 28 days thereafter using a passive surveillance system, reporting a total of 74 AEs in the intervention group (19 serious, six moderate and 49 mild) and 44 in the control group (four serious, seven moderate and 33 mild) (SAEs: RR 4.19, 95% CI 1.43-12.31; AEs: RR 1.48, 95% CI 0.12-18.02⁹).

Marasinghe 2020(19) monitored SAEs 1-5 months post-intervention and no serious events were reported during or after the treatment.

Tseroni 2015(20) recorded adverse events in 397 out of the 1094 treated individuals and the majority were classified as minor; predominantly dizziness and headache for chloroquine and abdominal pain for primaquine. A single case of primaquine-induced hemolysis was recorded in a person with an incorrect Glucose-6-Phosphate Dehydrogenase (G6PD) test. The total number of AEs reported was 688.

Effects reported on prevalence of infection among those targeted by the intervention

Prevalence of infection among the targeted populations was reported in the two cRCTs at 1-2 months post-intervention and during the last month of the intervention, respectively (**Clarke 2008**(17) and **Rehman 2019**(16)). **Clarke 2008**(17) reported lower prevalence in the intervention arm as compared to the control arm (adjusted RR 0.11, 95% CI 0.05-0.27¹⁰). **Rehman 2019**(16) also reported lower prevalence in the intervention arm as compared to the control arm (adjusted RR 0.22, 95% CI 0.16-0.30¹¹). When the effects were combined in a meta-analysis, the pooled effect showed a reduction in prevalence among those targeted by the drug administration when compared to no intervention (RR 0.15, 95% CI 0.06-0.38, p-value <0.001, **Figure 4**).

⁹ Not corrected for unit of analysis error because of extremely wide confidence intervals.

¹⁰ Fully adjusted for trial design, age, sex, age/sex interaction, bed net use, and migration history as reported in the article.

¹¹ Adjusted for age group, baseline community parasite prevalence, sex, bed net use, and region as reported in the article.

Figure 4. Effect of Targeted Drug Administration vs no Targeted Drug Administration on prevalence among the targeted population.

Opoku 2016(18) reported prevalence of infection among the targeted population 1 month post-intervention in the two intervention arms (one arm assessed the effect of artemether-lumefantrine and albendazole whereas the other assessed the effect of artemether-lumefantrine, albendazole and praziquantel) as compared to the control arm. The two intervention arms were pooled and compared with the control arm for analysis. The unadjusted pooled effect showed a reduction in prevalence among those targeted by the drug administration intervention when compared to no intervention (unadjusted RR 0.35, 95% CI 0.22-0.57, **Figure 5**).

Figure 5. Effect of Targeted Drug Administration vs no Targeted Drug Administration on prevalence among the targeted population.

The two uncontrolled before and after studies also reported on prevalence of infection among the targeted population. The study reported in **Marasinghe 2020**(19) was conducted in Sri Lanka, which had been free from indigenous cases for six consecutive years until the first introduced case was reported among the group of migrant workers targeted by drug administration. On the other hand, the study reported in **Tseroni 2015**(20) was conducted in an elimination setting that reported 10 locally acquired cases and 17 imported cases in the year prior to the intervention. Both studies reported no malaria cases during the follow-up periods of five months post-intervention (**Marasinghe 2020**(19)) and at least six months post-intervention (**Tseroni 2015**(20)).

Certainty of evidence

Prevalence of malaria infection at the community level

As reported by a single study (**Staedke 2018**(15)), at 1-4 months post-intervention, targeted drug administration resulted in little to no difference in prevalence of malaria infection at the community level (high certainty evidence but little to no effect size).

SAEs and AEs

As reported by **Clarke 2008**(17), targeted drug administration may have resulted in little to no difference in SAEs (low certainty evidence, little to no effect) and a slight increase in AEs (low certainty evidence, very wide confidence intervals). For **Staedke 2018**(15) and **Marasinghe 2020**(19), the evidence was very uncertain about the effect of targeted drug administration on SAEs (very low certainty evidence).

Prevalence of infection among those targeted by the intervention

For **Clarke 2008**(17) and **Rehman 2019**(16), targeted drug administration likely resulted in a large reduction in prevalence among those targeted by the intervention (moderate certainty evidence and large effect size). As reported by **Opoku 2016**(18), targeted drug administration may have resulted in a reduction in prevalence among those targeted by the intervention (low certainty of evidence, moderate effect size). For the two uncontrolled before and after studies (**Marasinghe 2020**(19) and **Tseroni 2015**(20)), the evidence was very uncertain about the effect of targeted drug administration on prevalence among those targeted by the intervention (very low certainty evidence).

Resource Use

Data on resource use for targeted drug administration was abstracted from one publication on costs and cost effectiveness (**Temperley 2008**(21)) linked to the school-based delivery of intermittent preventive treatment in western Kenya reported in **Clarke 2008**(17). The delivery of intermittent preventive treatment by teachers was estimated to cost US \$1.88 per child treated per year, with the largest cost components being drug and teacher training. The estimated cost per case of *P. falciparum* infection averted was US \$5.36. The publication concluded that intermittent preventive treatment administered by teachers compared favorably with the estimated costs of other interventions such as insecticide-treated nets or indoor residual spraying.

Acceptability

Acceptability of intermittent preventive treatment for malaria in school-children was reported in one qualitative research study (**Matangila 2017b**(22)), which aimed to understand the perceptions and experiences of parents and teachers related to intermittent preventive treatment after a clinical trial in two schools of Democratic Republic of the Congo. Most barriers were related to the perceived drug safety and the malaria-related knowledge in the community. Among the parents owning negative experiences related to intermittent preventive treatment in schools and therefore reluctant to the use of the strategy, wrong malaria-related knowledge, bad experiences with the treatments administered within the trial and misunderstanding of the strategy were the three key factors reported. Even though teachers were mostly eager to be trained to administer the drugs to pupils, most parents would prefer health workers rather

than teachers for the administration of the drugs. Contrary to the definition of intermittent preventive treatment itself, all the parents that accepted the strategy suggested the diagnosis of malaria before any drug administration.

Discussion

Summary of main results

Few studies contributed data to assess the effect of targeted drug administration on outcomes and overall, the certainty of the evidence was moderate-low. Based on results from a single trial, targeted drug administration results in little to no difference in prevalence of malaria infection at the community level. For prevalence among those targeted by the intervention as an intermediate outcome on the way to reduction of community transmission, pooled results from two randomized trials suggest that targeted drug administration likely results in a large reduction in prevalence among those targeted by the intervention. It is worth noting that these studies targeted school-children in moderate to high transmission settings, and that the effect of this outcome on community transmission depends on how important the targeted population as a reservoir of infection is in relation to the overall force of infection. The type of antimalarial drug administered, the number and frequency of rounds, background interventions, and coverage achieved are factors that may affect the impact of the intervention and should be considered. Two studies contributed data on contextual factors, highlighting the importance of affordability, cost-effectiveness and acceptability as key determinants when assessing a new malaria control intervention. Addressing any misperceptions about the intervention is imperative to increase the community's ownership and acceptability towards the intervention.

Five studies (six reports) were included in this review: two cRCTs, one controlled before and after study and two uncontrolled before and after studies. The two cRCTs were conducted in areas of moderate to high transmission, western Kenya and eastern Uganda. **Staedke 2018**(15) and **Rehman 2019**(16) assessed the effect of six monthly rounds of intermittent preventive treatment in school-aged children as compared to standard of care, and **Clarke 2008**(17) assessed the impact of three rounds of intermittent preventive treatment every four months in school-aged children as compared to placebo. The controlled before and after study, **Opoku 2016**(18), assessed the impact of three rounds of intermittent preventive treatment every three months in school-aged children as compared to no-intermittent preventive treatment. The two uncontrolled before and after studies included were conducted in areas of zero malaria transmission, Sri Lanka and Greece. **Marasinghe 2020**(19) targeted migrant workers in a factory construction site and assessed the effect of a single round of mass radical treatment. **Tseroni 2015**(20) targeted migrant farm laborers living in the epicenter of a previous malaria outbreak and also assessed the effect of a single round of mass radical treatment.

Prevalence of infection at the community level was only assessed in one study (**Staedke 2018**(15)). Based on the data reported in this cRCT, targeted drug administration results in little to no difference in prevalence of malaria infection at the community level 1-4 months post-intervention.

SAEs were assessed in the two cRCTs (**Staedke 2018(15)** and **Clarke 2008(17)**) and in one of the uncontrolled before and after studies (**Marasinghe 2020(19)**). For **Staedke 2018(15)**, the evidence is very uncertain about the effect of targeted drug administration on SAEs. Based on **Clarke 2008(17)**, targeted drug administration may result in little to no difference in SAEs, but the outcome was rated as very serious imprecision. AEs were assessed in one cRCT (**Clarke 2008(17)**) and one uncontrolled before and after study (**Tseroni 2015(20)**). Based on the cRCT, targeted drug administration may result in a slight increase in AEs, but the outcome was rated as very serious imprecision. The evidence assessed from **Tseroni 2015(20)** is very uncertain about the effect of targeted drug administration on AEs.

Prevalence of infection among those targeted by the intervention was used as an intermediate outcome for prevalence at the community level. In the case where the intervention group may have seen benefit, this cannot fully be considered indicative of a potential community impact. In contrast, if there is no benefit in the intervention group, we can be relatively sure this would be consistent at the community level. The outcome was assessed in all five included studies. Based on the data from the two cRCTs (**Clarke 2008(17)** and **Rehman 2019(16)**), targeted drug administration likely results in a large reduction in prevalence among those targeted by the intervention from the last month of the intervention to two months post-intervention. The certainty of the evidence for the controlled before and after study (**Opoku 2016(18)**) was low. Based on its data, targeted drug administration may result in a reduction in prevalence among those targeted by the intervention at one month post-intervention. For the two uncontrolled before and after studies (**Marasinghe 2020(19)** and **Tseroni 2015(20)**), the evidence is very uncertain about the effect of targeted drug administration on prevalence among those targeted by the intervention.

The intent of the “targeted strategies” is to identify the groups that have the highest exposure to infected mosquitoes as they will likely account for the vast majority of the reservoir of infection. In southeast Asia, for example, forested areas are one of the remaining foci of malaria transmission, and forest workers are a population highly exposed to malaria for limited periods of time who could benefit from targeted drug administration, as they would be protected during the periods of exposure. Likewise, migrant labors or refugees originating from a malaria endemic region could be another high-risk population that could benefit from this type of interventions. Even though it seems that targeting these groups would probably be most relevant in low to very low transmission settings, the PICO questions for this review were not limited to this specific transmission strata, so studies conducted in moderate to high transmission areas also met the criteria for inclusion. Intermittent preventive treatment in school-children was included for review, as school-aged children were considered high-risk groups and it has been shown that they are significant reservoirs of human-to-mosquito transmission(23,24). We excluded other forms of chemoprevention in high-risk groups such as intermittent preventive treatment in pregnancy, intermittent preventive treatment in infants, or seasonal malaria chemoprevention due to the fact that, even though the strategies target high-risk groups, these are interventions already recommended by the WHO, and our goal was not to reconsider the current guidance or assess the impact of those strategies. To specifically assess studies that have targeted populations thought to be important reservoirs of infection, the PICO questions of future iterations of the targeted strategies reviews could probably either be restricted to very low to low transmission settings or to populations proven to host the vast majority of the reservoir of infection.

Overall, the certainty of evidence for outcomes in this review was based on a small number of included studies. Moreover, when stratification by study design and outcome reported was done and after assessing heterogeneity between studies, few syntheses could be made, limiting the evidence for most of the outcomes to single studies. We excluded many studies because they did not meet the criteria for inclusion due to reasons such as individual-randomization or imbalanced background interventions across arms. Notwithstanding, these studies can provide useful information for policymakers.

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Other information

Registration and protocol

The review protocol has been registered in the International Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews (PROSPERO), registration number CRD42021237822.

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Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Availability of data, code, and other materials

The review documents including data templates/forms and detailed data extracted from included studies are available by request and primary information on included studies available in MESA Track. Data analyses and code are not publicly available since they were conducted in a subscription-based software (Eppi-Reviewer).

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Characteristics of studies

Characteristics of included studies

Staedke 2018 and Rehman 2019

Study characteristics	
<i>METHODS</i>	
Study dates	2014-2015
Location	Jinja District, eastern Uganda
Peak transmission season	Perennial transmission
Baseline transmission intensity	Moderate, baseline cluster parasite prevalence (median) was 25.4% in the intervention group and 25.2% in the control group
Parasite species	<i>Plasmodium falciparum</i>
Vector species	<i>Anopheles gambiae</i> , <i>Anopheles funestus</i> , <i>Anopheles arabiensis</i>
Study design	Cluster-randomized controlled trial
Statistical power calculation	Assuming significance of 5% and power of 80%, authors calculated that 105 individuals per cluster (minimum total 8820) would allow detection of a relative reduction in parasite prevalence of 29%, based on 21% prevalence in the control group
Clusters	<u>Unit of randomization</u> : Primary school + 100 closest households <u>Features of the clusters</u> : Buffer areas, restricted randomization <u>Number of clusters selected</u> : 84 <u>Number of clusters analyzed</u> : 84 <u>Average cluster size</u> : 35 households, 119 participants (median)
<i>PARTICIPANTS</i>	
Targeted population	<u>Total</u> : 42 351* <u>Intervention</u> : 23 280 students in intervention group eligible for IPT, 3030 households screened for baseline community survey, 2097 households approached for final community survey <u>Comparison</u> : 2957 households screened for baseline community survey, 2160 households approached for final community survey
Participant characteristics	School-aged children, 5 to 20 years
<i>INTERVENTION</i>	
Intervention	Intermittent preventive treatment
Comparator	Standard of care

Systematic Review on Targeted Drug Administration

Background interventions	No background interventions described
Drug and manufacturer	Dihydroartemisinin- piperazine, Duo-Cotexcin tablets (Beijing Holley-Cotec Pharmaceuticals, Beijing, China)
Dosage	40 mg dihydroartemisinin and 320 mg piperazine
Number of rounds per season or year	6
Treatment interval	Monthly
Duration of the intervention	6 months
Treatment adherence	Round 1: 2680 (12%), Round 2: 3287 (14%), Round 3: 3601 (15%), Round 4: 8154 (36%), Round 5: 8628 (37%), Round 6: 6714 (29%)
OUTCOMES	
Prevalence of infection at the community level	<u>Measurement:</u> Cross-sectional community surveys in randomly-selected households, measured by microscopy <u>Timepoints:</u> 1-4 months post-intervention <u>Sample size:</u> 4455 (intervention); 4467 (control)
Serious Adverse Events	All intervention participants were monitored for serious adverse events, and a subset of participants selected by convenience sampling for cardiac monitoring. 17 serious adverse events were reported, including two deaths (one from a road traffic accident and one from a tetanus infection, both unrelated to the drug). Among the remaining 15 serious adverse events, two (an allergic skin reaction and a case of weakness and loss of consciousness after severe abdominal pain that was attributed to hypoglycemia) were judged to be possibly related to the drug.
Prevalence of infection among those targeted by the intervention	<u>Measurement:</u> Cross-sectional survey of randomly-selected children from each participating school <u>Timepoints:</u> Toward the end of the intervention, month 0 <u>Sample size:</u> 546 (intervention); 546 (control)

*Intervention: 23 280 students in intervention group eligible for IPT + 5037 residents screened for baseline community survey + 4477 residents screened for final community survey; Control: 5038 residents screened for baseline community survey + 4519 residents screened for final community survey.

Risk of bias		
<i>Outcome: Prevalence of infection at the community level</i>		
Domain	Author's judgement	Justification
D1a: Randomization process	Low risk	"Used restricted randomization to ensure balance across clusters for geographical location by subcounty and school type (public or private)."
D1b: Timing of identification or recruitment of participants	Low risk	"Study personnel enrolled primary schools after cluster randomization without masking of study group allocation. An information sheet described the study and verbal consent to participate was obtained after

		randomization". Baseline characteristics were similar across study groups.
D2: Deviations from the intended interventions	Low risk	Nothing to indicate that the intervention had any deviations from its intended format based on the trial context.
D3: Missing outcome data	Low risk	Data reported for all clusters. "Sample size calculations for the final community survey were informed by data collected in the baseline survey."
D4: Measurement of the outcome	Low risk	Outcomes "read by experienced laboratory technologists who were unaware of study group assignments."
D5: Selection of the reported result	Low risk	Reported primary and secondary outcomes are the same as reported on clinicaltrials.gov.

Risk of bias

Outcome: Serious Adverse Events

Domain	Author's judgement	Justification
D1a: Randomization process	Low risk	"Used restricted randomization to ensure balance across clusters for geographical location by subcounty and school type (public or private)."
D1b: Timing of identification or recruitment of participants	Low risk	Not applicable based on study design. "Study personnel enrolled primary schools after cluster randomization without masking of study group allocation. An information sheet described the study and verbal consent to participate was obtained after randomization". Baseline characteristics were similar across study groups.
D2: Deviations from the intended interventions	Low risk	Nothing to indicate that the intervention had any deviations from its intended format based on the trial context.
D3: Missing outcome data	High risk	Adverse events were not monitored in the control arm.
D4: Measurement of the outcome	Low risk	"All intervention participants were monitored for serious adverse events, and a subset of participants selected by convenience sampling for cardiac monitoring."
D5: Selection of the reported result	Low risk	Reported primary and secondary outcomes are the same as reported on clinicaltrials.gov.

Risk of bias

Outcome: Prevalence of infection among those targeted by the intervention

Domain	Author's judgement	Justification
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D1a: Randomization process	Low risk	“Used restricted randomization to ensure balance across clusters for geographical location by subcounty and school type (public or private).”
D1b: Timing of identification or recruitment of participants	Low risk	Not applicable based on study design. “Study personnel enrolled primary schools after cluster randomization without masking of study group allocation. An information sheet described the study and verbal consent to participate was obtained after randomization”. Baseline characteristics were similar across study groups.
D2: Deviations from the intended interventions	Low risk	Nothing to indicate that the intervention had any deviations from its intended format based on the trial context.
D3: Missing outcome data	Low risk	Data reported for all clusters. “Sample size was determined for the trial’s secondary outcome, smear positive microscopy among school children, and was refined after results from the baseline survey were available.”
D4: Measurement of the outcome	Low risk	Outcomes “read by experienced laboratory technologists who were unaware of study group assignments.”
D5: Selection of the reported result	Low risk	Reported primary and secondary outcomes are the same as reported on clinicaltrials.gov.

Clarke 2008

Study characteristics	
<i>METHODS</i>	
Study dates	2005-2006
Location	Bondo District, western Kenya
Peak transmission season	March-May and November-December
Baseline transmission intensity	High, baseline parasite prevalence was 41% in the intervention group and 42% in the control group
Parasite species	<i>Plasmodium falciparum</i>
Vector species	Not described
Study design	Cluster-randomized controlled trial
Statistical power calculation	80% power to detect a 30% reduction in the prevalence of anaemia in the intervention group compared with placebo at 5% significance
Clusters	<u>Unit of randomization:</u> Primary school <u>Features of the clusters:</u> Stratification <u>Number of clusters selected:</u> 30

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	<u>Number of clusters analyzed</u> : 30 <u>Average cluster size</u> : 225
<i>PARTICIPANTS</i>	
Targeted population	<u>Total</u> : 6758 <u>Intervention</u> : 3535 <u>Comparison</u> : 3223
Participant characteristics	School-aged children, 5 to 18 years
<i>INTERVENTION</i>	
Intervention	Intermittent preventive treatment
Comparator	Placebo
Background interventions	Mass treatment with anthelmintics
Drug and manufacturer	Sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine + amodiaquine, Cosmos Limited
Dosage	Sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine: single dose given over one day; amodiaquine: 3 daily doses over 3 days. Dosage given according to age.
Number of rounds per season or year	3
Treatment interval	Every 4 months
Duration of the intervention	1 year
Treatment adherence	1070 (41%) received treatment on all 9 days
<i>OUTCOMES</i>	
Serious Adverse Events	Adverse events were monitored by the study team for 3 days after each treatment, and a further 28 days thereafter using a passive surveillance system in schools and local health centres. 23 serious adverse events were reported within 28 days of treatment, 19 in the intervention group (of which three were judged to be possibly associated with treatment), and 4 in the control group.
Adverse Events	Adverse events were monitored by the study team for 3 days after each treatment, and a further 28 days thereafter using a passive surveillance system in schools and local health centres. A total of 74 adverse events (including serious, moderate and mild) were reported in the intervention arm, and 44 in the control arm.
Prevalence of infection among those targeted by the intervention	<u>Measurement</u> : Cross-sectional survey <u>Timepoints</u> : Approximately 6 weeks (1-2 months) post-intervention <u>Sample size</u> : 2584 (intervention); 2294 (control)
Risk of bias	
<i>Outcome: AEs (including SAEs)</i>	

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Domain	Author's judgement	Justification
D1a: Randomization process	Low risk	"Schools were randomly allocated to one of six coded drug groups by use of block randomization according to a computer-generated random number list by an investigator blind to the drug group."
D1b: Timing of identification or recruitment of participants	Low risk	"Ten schools were randomly selected from each school-performance stratum, and within each stratum schools were randomly allocated to one of six coded drug groups by use of block randomization according to a computer generated random number list by an investigator blind to drug group."
D2: Deviations from the intended interventions	Low risk	"Active drugs and placebos were similar in size and shape, but differed in taste. To preserve blinding, staff responsible for measuring health or education outcomes were unaware of drug group allocation, and analysis was done by a statistician with no previous involvement in the trial."
D3: Missing outcome data	Low risk	"Adverse events were monitored by the study team for 3 days after each treatment, and a further 28 days thereafter using a passive surveillance system in schools and local health centres."
D4: Measurement of the outcome	Low risk	"Staff responsible for measuring health and education outcomes were unaware of drug group allocation, and analysis was done by a statistician with no previous involvement in the trial."
D5: Selection of the reported result	Low risk	"An independent data safety monitoring board monitored the trial and approved the analysis plan." Reported primary and secondary outcomes are the same as reported on clinicaltrials.gov.

Risk of bias		
<i>Outcome: Prevalence of infection among those targeted by the intervention</i>		
Domain	Author's judgement	Justification
D1a: Randomization process	Low risk	"Schools were randomly allocated to one of six coded drug groups by use of block randomization according to a computer-generated random number list by an investigator blind to the drug group."
D1b: Timing of identification or recruitment of participants	Low risk	"Ten schools were randomly selected from each school-performance stratum, and within each stratum schools were randomly allocated to one of six coded drug groups by use of block randomization according to a computer generated

		random number list by an investigator blind to drug group.”
D2: Deviations from the intended interventions	Low risk	“Active drugs and placebos were similar in size and shape, but differed in taste. To preserve blinding, staff responsible for measuring health or education outcomes were unaware of drug group allocation, and analysis was done by a statistician with no previous involvement in the trial.”
D3: Missing outcome data	Low risk	“73% of children enrolled were examined in the postintervention survey 12 months later. Numbers of children lost to follow-up was similar in intervention and control groups.”
D4: Measurement of the outcome	Low risk	“Staff responsible for measuring health and education outcomes were unaware of drug group allocation, and analysis was done by a statistician with no previous involvement in the trial.”
D5: Selection of the reported result	Low risk	“An independent data safety monitoring board monitored the trial and approved the analysis plan.” Reported primary and secondary outcomes are the same as reported on clinicaltrials.gov.

Opoku 2016

Study characteristics	
<i>METHODS</i>	
Study dates	2011-2012
Location	Kassena-Nankana Districts, Upper East Region, Ghana
Peak transmission season	May-November
Baseline transmission intensity	Moderate, prevalence of malaria parasitemia was 28.7% among the schoolchildren at baseline
Parasite species	<i>Plasmodium falciparum</i>
Vector species	<i>Anopheles gambiae</i> , <i>Anopheles funestus</i> , <i>Anopheles arabiensis</i>
Study design	Three-arm, open-label, before-after intervention study including a control arm
Statistical power calculation	No power calculation conducted; purposive sampling ensured a fair representation of the districts based on previous data on <i>Schistosoma haematobium</i> and malaria transmission
Clusters	Not applicable
PARTICIPANTS	
Targeted population	Total: 348 Intervention: 131 (arm 1), 90 (arm 2) Comparison: 127

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Participant characteristics	School-aged children, 6 to 15 years
<i>INTERVENTION</i>	
Intervention	Intermittent preventive treatment
Comparator	Mass treatment with anthelmintics
Background interventions	Mass treatment with anthelmintics
Drug and manufacturer	Artemether-lumefantrine
Dosage	20/120, standard 3-day schedule according to body weight
Number of rounds per season or year	3
Treatment interval	Every 3 months
Duration of the intervention	7 months
Treatment adherence	Not described
<i>OUTCOMES</i>	
Prevalence of infection among those targeted by the intervention	<u>Measurement:</u> Parasitemia determined by microscopy <u>Timepoints:</u> 1 month post-intervention <u>Sample size:</u> 131 (arm 1); 90 (arm 2); 63.5 (control)*

*Sample size in the control arm used for the analysis has been 63.5 instead of 127 to account for the two intervention arms compared to the control arm.

Risk of bias		
<i>Outcome: Prevalence of infection among those targeted by the intervention</i>		
Domain	Author's judgement	Justification
D1: Bias due to confounding	Moderate risk	Crude prevalence proportions based on the study participants without accounting for other potential influences to study outcomes
D2: Bias due to selection of participants	Low risk	All participants who would have been eligible for the target trial were included in the study; for each participant, start of follow up and start of intervention coincided
D3: Bias in classification of interventions	Low risk	Intervention status is well defined
D4: Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	Moderate risk	"Because of limitations due to funding constrains, and expansion to accommodate other thematic areas, the study, which was initially planned as a randomized controlled trial, had to be changed to a before-after design."

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D5: Bias due to missing data	Low risk	97% follow-up
D6: Bias in measurement of outcomes	Unclear	No description of blinding of outcome assessment
D7: Bias in selection of the reported result	Low risk	Reported primary and secondary outcomes are the same as reported on clinicaltrials.gov

Marasinghe 2020

Study characteristics	
<i>METHODS</i>	
Study dates	2018
Location	Monaragala District, Southwestern Sri Lanka
Peak transmission season	Not applicable
Baseline transmission intensity	Zero
Parasite species	<i>Plasmodium vivax</i>
Vector species	<i>Anopheles culicifacies</i>
Study design	Uncontrolled before and after
Statistical power calculation	Not applicable
Clusters	Not applicable
<i>PARTICIPANTS</i>	
Targeted population	<u>Total</u> : 31 <u>Intervention</u> : 31 <u>Comparison</u> : not applicable
Participant characteristics	Migrant workers of Indian origin in a factory construction site
<i>INTERVENTION</i>	
Intervention	Mass radical treatment
Comparator	Not applicable
Background interventions	No background interventions described
Drug and manufacturer	Chloroquine and primaquine
Dosage	Chloroquine 25 mg/kg body weight (over three days) and primaquine low dose (0.25 mg/kg/day bodyweight for 14 days)
Number of rounds per season or year	Single round

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Treatment interval	Not applicable
Duration of the intervention	6 months
Treatment adherence	All 31 individuals received the full course of chloroquine 24 individuals received primaquine for 14 days, the others were excluded due to G6PD deficiency
<i>OUTCOMES</i>	
Serious Adverse Events	Participants were monitored daily for the occurrence of adverse events until completion of the treatment and all were followed up at monthly intervals for a period of five months. No major adverse effects were reported during or after the treatment.
Prevalence of infection among those targeted by the intervention	<u>Measurement</u> : Parasitemia determined by microscopy <u>Timepoints</u> : 5 months post-intervention <u>Sample size</u> : 31 (intervention)

Risk of bias	
<i>Outcome: All outcomes</i>	
Critical overall risk of bias due to the inherent biases associated with the study design	

Tseroni 2015

Study characteristics	
<i>METHODS</i>	
Study dates	2013-2014
Location	Evrotas, southern Greece
Peak transmission season	May-December
Baseline transmission intensity	In 2012, 10 locally acquired cases and 17 imported cases were recorded in the area in an elimination setting preventing malaria reintroduction
Parasite species	<i>Plasmodium vivax</i>
Vector species	<i>Anopheles sacharovi</i>
Study design	Uncontrolled before and after
Statistical power calculation	Not applicable
Clusters	Not applicable
<i>PARTICIPANTS</i>	
Targeted population	<u>Total</u> : 1270 <u>Intervention</u> : 1270 <u>Comparison</u> : not applicable
Participant characteristics	Migrant farm laborers living in the epicenter of the 2011 outbreak

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<i>INTERVENTION</i>	
Intervention	Mass radical treatment
Comparator	Not applicable
Background interventions	Community education, active case detection, vector control (IRS and LLINs)
Drug and manufacturer	Chloroquine and primaquine
Dosage	Chloroquine in the form of bisphosphate salts at an initial dose of 1000mg (620mg base) followed by 500mg at 6, 24 and 48 hours. Primaquine tablets were administered for 14 days at a dose of 30mg base per day (high dose)
Number of rounds per season or year	Single round
Treatment interval	Not applicable
Duration of the intervention	Two years
Treatment adherence	87.3% individuals successfully completed the treatment
<i>OUTCOMES</i>	
Adverse Events	All adverse effects were systematically recorded in structured pharmacovigilance forms, and were promptly treated by the health professionals from the field team. 688 adverse events were recorded in 397 individuals, the vast majority minor, predominantly dizziness and headache for chloroquine (284 events) and abdominal pain (85 events) for primaquine. A single case of primaquine-induced hemolysis was recorded in a person whose initial G6PD test proved incorrect.
Prevalence of infection among those targeted by the intervention	<u>Measurement:</u> Weekly fever screening visits in the context of active case detection. A rapid diagnostic test for malaria was performed to all individuals with fever or who reported fever and/or other malaria compatible symptoms during the previous week and blood was drawn for blood smear and molecular diagnosis of malaria. <u>Timepoints:</u> Follow-up at least six months <u>Sample size:</u> 1094

Risk of bias
<i>Outcome: All outcomes</i>
Critical overall risk of bias due to the inherent biases associated with the study design

Characteristics of excluded studies

Study	Reference	Reason for exclusion
Ahmed 2019	(25)	Incorrect population
Ambroise-Thomas 2001	(26)	Incorrect intervention: Prophylaxis; Report could not be retrieved
Anonymous 1948	(27)	Report could not be retrieved

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Anonymous 2016	(28)	Study focus area
Armauer 2020	(29)	Incorrect intervention: Reactive TDA
Barger 2009	(30)	Study design: individual randomization
Bennett 2020	(31)	Incorrect intervention: Reactive TDA; Cross-referenced study: Finn (2020), Silumbe (2020)
Betuela 2012	(32)	Study design: individual randomization
Bigira 2014	(33)	Study design: individual randomization
Boivin 2016	(34)	Cross-referenced article: Bigira 2014
Boivin 2014	(35)	Cross-referenced article: Bigira 2014; Abstract only/could not be retrieved
Breeveld 2012	(36)	Study focus area: review
Buchwald 2018	(37)	Abstract only/could not be retrieved
Chandramohan 2005	(38)	Incorrect intervention: other strategy (IPTi)
Clarke 2012	(39)	Abstract only/could not be retrieved
Clarke 2017	(40)	Imbalance of background interventions: teacher-led participatory malaria prevention education implemented only in intervention arm
Cohee 2018	(41)	Imbalance of background interventions: peer education program implemented only in intervention arm Study design: individual randomization
Dantzer 2017	(42)	Abstract only/could not be retrieved; Incorrect intervention: no TDA
Dicko 2008	(43)	Incorrect intervention: expanded SMC
Dobaño 2019	(44)	Not the correct outcomes reported
Edstein 2001	(45)	Study design: individual randomization
Finn 2020	(46)	Cross referenced article: Bennett (2020), Silumbe (2020); Incorrect intervention: Reactive TDA
Grobusch 2007	(47)	Incorrect intervention: other strategy (IPTi)
Guyant 2015	(48)	Study focus area
Hill 2016	(49)	Incorrect population
Houel 1954	(50)	Incorrect intervention: Prophylaxis
Hoyt 2018	(51)	Incorrect population
Hygiene 2008	(52)	Study design: individual randomization
Huch 2018	(53)	Abstract only/could not be retrieved
Janssens 1955	(54)	Report could not be retrieved
Landier 2016	(55)	Protocol only; Incorrect population: not targeted to high-risk groups, targeted to higher incidence hotspots; Cross-referenced article: Sahan (2017)
Liljander 2010	(56)	Incorrect intervention: SMC
Lon 2015	(57)	Cross-reference: Manning 2018; Abstract only
Lwin 2012	(58)	Study design: individual randomization
Makenga 2020	(59)	Protocol only; Cross-referenced study: National 2019
Manning 2018	(60)	Inappropriate comparison; Protocol only; Cross-referenced study: Lon (2015)
Manore 2019	(61)	Study focus area

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Matangila 2017	(62)	Study design: individual randomization
Miller 1955	(63)	Study design: controlled before and after, but only 1 site per arm
MSF 2020	(64)	Ongoing study with no results available yet; Abstract only
Nankabirwa 2010	(65)	Cross-referenced study: Hygiene 2008
Nankabirwa 2014	(66)	Study design: individual randomization
National 2019	(67)	Protocol only; Cross-referenced study: Makenga 2020
Nikolov 2017	(68)	Incorrect population: not targeted to high-risk groups; Abstract only
Rohner 2010	(69)	Study design: individual randomization
Sahan 2017	(70)	Incorrect population: not targeted to high-risk groups, targeted to higher incidence hotspots; Cross-referenced article: Landier (2016)
Silumbe 2020	(71)	Incorrect intervention: Reactive TDA; Cross-referenced article: Finn (2020), Bennett (2020)
Son 2017	(72)	Study design: individual randomization
Steketee 1996	(73)	Incorrect intervention: IPTp
Stingl 2004	(74)	Report could not be retrieved
Thera 2018	(75)	Study design: individual randomization
Tuck 2005	(76)	Incorrect intervention: no TDA
UCSF 2019	(77)	Ongoing study with no results available yet
Villegas 2010	(78)	Incorrect intervention: no TDA; Abstract only
von Seidlein 2019	(79)	Study focus area: review
Wen 2016	(80)	Incorrect intervention: no TDA
Xu 2021	(81)	Study focus area: review

Reasons for exclusion

Reason for exclusion	
Incorrect intervention	Chemoprophylaxis
	Other strategy such as MDA, IPTi, SMC, etc.
	Drug administration with previous testing (TTaT)
	Reactive TDA
Incorrect population	Not the right treatment dose
	Not in adults and children at increased risk of malaria infection based on risk factors
Incorrect study focus area	Study evaluates the efficacy of antimalarials, drug regimens/ dosing, diagnostic tests, supply chain, resource management, access to care, and/or quality of care and does not use the TDA intervention design
Background interventions	Imbalance of background interventions
Inappropriate comparison	Compared to another intervention without a control group
Incorrect study design	Does not meet study design criteria
Intervention implementation criteria	Time frame does not include 1-24 months after the start of the intervention
	Follow-up periods for intervention and control groups are not the same

	Timing of baseline and endline surveys are not at the same time in intervention and control groups
	Length of pre-/ post-intervention periods for ITS studies are different (or cover different seasons)
Outcomes	Not the correct outcomes reported
Cross-referenced article	Supplementary article to a primary study already included/excluded
Ongoing study with no results available yet/report could not be retrieved	Ongoing study, report not retrieved
Abstract or protocol only/report could not be retrieved	Abstract, protocol or another document for which the full-text report could not be retrieved

Ongoing studies

Study	Reference	Notes
Makenga 2020	(59)	Protocol
MSF 2020	(64)	Available in MESA Track ¹² Contextual factors
UCSF 2019	(77)	Available in MESA Track ¹³ Contextual factors Results planned for the end of 2021

¹²<http://www.mesamalaria.org/mesa-track/mass-drug-administration-long-acting-antimalarials-among-children-bossangoa-health>

¹³<http://www.mesamalaria.org/mesa-track/targeting-malaria-high-risk-populations-tailored-intervention-packages-study-assess>

Appendix 1. Search Strategy

Database: Ovid MEDLINE(R) and In-Process & Other Non-Indexed Citations <1946 to November 03, 2020>

1	*malaria/
2	exp malaria, falciparum/ or exp malaria, vivax/
3	malaria ovale.mp. or Plasmodium ovale/
4	plasmodium malariae.mp. or Plasmodium malariae/
5	1 or 2 or 3 or 4
6	Antimalarials/
7	Disease Eradication/ or elimination.tw
8	(tailored adj2 (intervention* or treatment* or strateg* or administration)).tw
9	(relapse adj2 prevention).mp
10	Presumptive adj2 (treatment or therapy).tw
11	focal adj2 (drug administration).tw or “focal MDA”.tw
12	targeted adj2 (intervention* or treatment or strateg* or administration).tw
13	6 or 7 or 8 or 9 or 10 or 11 or 12
14	(“Forest-goers “ or Forests/ or Vulnerable or Worksites or Farm* OR plantation* or mining or miner* or Miners/ or laborers or cultivators or military or “armed forces” or Military Personnel/ or “peace-keepers” or agricultural)
15	“high risk population*”.mp. or Risk Factors/
16	“special populations”.tw
17	“high exposure”.tw or “highly exposed”.tw or “high transmission”.tw or hotspot*.tw
18	14 or 15 or 16 or 17
19	5 and 13 and 18

Appendix 2. Selection process and data extraction (methods)

Figure i. Process Flow Diagram for Review Methodology

Process for including studies based on review question PICO criteria for synthesis and meta-analysis in parallel to systematic inclusion of contextual evidence that was integrated with results to support the guideline development panel in formulating final strategy recommendations.

Figure ii. Adapted PRISMA Flow Diagram for Study Synthesis

Table i. Variables for data extraction from included studies

Study design	Experimental	Cluster-randomized controlled trials Cluster-randomized crossover trials Cluster-randomized stepped wedge designs Cluster-randomized factorial designs Quasi-experimental cluster controlled trials Controlled before and after studies Interrupted time series (ITS) Uncontrolled before and after studies Before and after studies with historical controls
	Observational	Prospective Cohort Case-control Cross-sectional Qualitative
	Mathematical modelling studies	
Setting	Country	Region District Village
	Environment	Urban or rural
	Transmission	Season Endemicity Transmission intensity
Demographics	Population size	
	Study population	Sample size
	Participant characteristics	Age Gender Other
Methodology	Diagnosis	
	Diagnostic tool	
Treatment	Drug and manufacturer	
	Dosage	
	Treatment adherence	
	Number of rounds per season/year	
	Number of years of the intervention	
Time period	Study period	Baseline length Intervention length Post-intervention length

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Infectious agent	Parasite species	
Baseline data	Pre-intervention measures	Incidence Prevalence
	Background interventions	Vector control Insecticide-treated nets Surveillance Availability of G6PD screening
	Coverage of background interventions	
	Level of importation of drug-resistant parasites	
Intervention	Intervention population coverage	Target Actual
	Intervention arms	
	Control arms	
Outcomes	Epidemiological measures by sex/gender	Incidence of malaria infection Prevalence of malaria infection Elimination (defined as 0 indigenous or local cases for a period during the transmission season) Incidence of clinical malaria or number of indigenous malaria cases Drug resistance Adverse events
Other	Contextual study information	
	Potential study biases	
Source of funds	Study sponsors	
	Implementers	

Appendix 3. PRISMA Flow Diagram

*Reporting the number of records identified from each database or register searched and the total number across all databases and registers.

**Some of the reports assessed for eligibility have also been assessed for contextual factors and/or modelling.

Adapted From: Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* 2021;372:n71. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71. For more information, visit: <http://www.prisma-statement.org/>

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*Reporting the number of records identified from each database or register searched and the total number across all databases and registers.

**Some of the reports assessed for eligibility have also been assessed for contextual factors and/or modelling.

Adapted From: Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* 2021;372:n71. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71. For more information, visit: <http://www.prisma-statement.org/>

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